

EFFECT OF ORGANIZATIONAL COMMITMENTS ON PERFORMANCE OF NON-GOVERNMENTAL ORGANIZATIONS IN NAIROBI COUNTY

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Abstract: The main objective of the study was to establish the effect of organizational commitments on performance of Non-governmental organizations in Nairobi County. The study was premised on four theories namely social exchange theory, co-operative game theory, resource-based theory and Stakeholders theory. A descriptive research design was used for the study. Primary information was used for the study which was assembled using semi structured questionnaires. The first section of the questionnaire collected bio data information of the respondents while the other sections had questions from the four variables of the study. The target population was 53 non-governmental organizations operating in Nairobi County. The unit of observation was managers from the three levels of management that is the lower level, middle level and top-level managers 3 managers were selected from each of the fifty three non-governmental organizations for the study. A sample of 112 managers was selected for the study. Collected information was scrutinized for descriptive, inferential correlation and regression analysis. Statistical Package for Social Sciences version 24 was used for Data Analysis. Study outcomes was displayed in form of frequency tables, percentages, and charts. Data results found out that Organizational Commitment, significantly and positively influence the performance of non – governmental organizations (NGOs) in Nairobi County. The study recommends that NGOs in Nairobi County embrace Organizational Commitment.

Keywords: Non-Governmental Organizations, Performance, Organizational Commitments.

1. INTRODUCTION

According to Mkutano and Sang (2018), some of the internal dynamics affecting the operations of NGOs in Kenya are, Organizational commitments, Collaborations with other organizations, capacity building on its employees and strategic control of the organization. Organizational commitment can be said to be a belief or culture held by the organization in the industry. In addition, organizational commitment can be the connection the organization and its stakeholders whereby the goals of both the organization and the shareholders are congruent (Renyut, Modding, Bima, & Sukmawati, 2017). Three types of organizational commitments exists in a firm namely, affective commitment, which is an affection of an employee towards his job, continuance commitment which is the fear of the employee to lose his job and lastly, the normative commitment which is the sense of obligation of an employee to staying a given job over a given period of time (Oyeniyi, Adeyemi, & Olaoye, 2017).

Organizational commitment can be achieved through several ways which may lead to improving the operations of the NGOs in the long run. Some of the ways are, through creating a strong teamwork culture whereby employees works together as a team, goals being clearly communicate to the members of staff and the organization's expectations from the respective staff, being transparent and encouraging open communication within the organization, Having and maintaining

good work ethics within the organization, fostering a progressive work culture, developing trust between the organization and its employees and amongst the employees and Encouraging innovation ideas from the employees (Shahida, 2019). All these aspects may help in improving organizational commitment and thus leading to improved performance of the NGO Organization.

Collaboration is the aspect of having employees being given a greater responsibility and a chance to air their views ,interact with their colleagues and managers and in so doing have a contribution on how the organization is run and the path the organization is charting (Kobani, 2020). In addition, Collaboration can be said to be how an organization works with others to achieve a common goal (Barasa, Simiyu, & Iravo, 2019). Through collaboration, organizations can achieve great goals which could not be achieved were it to be done individually. Collaboration is considered important as it is one of the internal dynamics which may lead to enhancement of the operations of an NGO.

Capacity building can be explained as the practice of emerging and reinforcing the skills, instinct, abilities ,processes and resources that an organization or entity needs to survive, adapt and thrive (Nwankwo, Olabisi, & Onwuchekwa, 2017). Through capacity building, the capabilities of an organization are enhanced and thus it is able to perform better than before capacity building was conducted. Capacity building empowers NGOs and their leaders to cultivate capacities and skills that makes them more efficient and effective and therefore increasing their capability for charitable nonprofits to enrich the lives and solve society's social challenges (Tukunimulongo, 2017).

Strategic control entails monitoring and evaluation of plans activities and results of an organization with a view aimed at the future ,giving a warning signal through evaluating information and activating suitable intervention either through tactical adjustments or strategic rearrangement Strategic control helps an organization to ensure proper actions are undertaken to achieve a strategic goal in the organization and to ensure these actions have the proper impact in the organization (Gaturu, Waiganjo, Bichang'a, & Oigo, 2017).

2. STATEMENT OF THE PROBLEM

The NGOs in Kenya play a key part in the expansion of the economy by providing job opportunities to the citizens and provision of essential services to compliment the government of the day. NGOs have been involved in the economy on areas of poverty eradication, provision of education to the less fortunate in the society and also uplifting the living standards of people in the society (NGOs co-ordination Board, 2019). Most NGOs in Kenya are confronted with probability of failure from the effect of fluctuating economic environments in the donor Nations which calls for prudent supervision and optimization of performance to guarantee existence if not stability or growth. According to the NGO co-ordination board, (2019),the performance of NGOs in Kenya has been affected by various aspects among them lack of capacity building among its employees, lack of strategic control within the organization and also lack of organizational commitment to achieve efficiency (NGOs co-ordination Board, 2019). In 2019, the NGOs co-ordination board had registered 11,262 NGOs in the country and at the same time, 2468 NGOs had been deregistered by the board (OAG, 2018). This was prompted by poor performance of the organizations which led to going concern issues and stoppage of funding by the stakeholders (Mkutano & Sang, 2018). In addition, 85% of the NGOs in Kenya did not achieve their set target and the reasons given for their failure is among them absence of organization dedication from its management to the course of the organization, lack of training of employees on new skills, failure of the organization to collaborate with other stakeholders to foster good relationships and lack of strategic control. Consequently, the funding of NGOs in Kenya has greatly shrunk due to the poor performance and failure to achieve their set work plan targets because the donors were not satisfied with the operations of the organizations (NGOs co-ordination Board, 2019). It is in the background of these challenges that has informed the study of the four variables under study. Different studies have been undertaken to find out the factors affecting performance of NGOs in Kenya and they have given rise to varied results.

Most of the studies concerning the performance of NGOs have been undertaken in developed Countries and there is scarcity of literature on the NGOs in Kenya. (Kimunguyi, Memba, & Njeru, 2015). Most of the research have presented conceptual, contextual, and methodological gaps. Conceptually, Mkutano and Sang (2018) commenced a review to understand the determinants of operations which define the effectiveness of NGOs in Kenya. This research looked at two variables; collaboration and capacity building and did not review the other variables being reviewed by the present study.

Contextually, research undertaken in Malaysia by Hanaysha, (2016) determined that employee empowerment through capacity building and organizational commitments were key determinants on the functioning of enterprises. This review did not review the determinants of performance of NGOs in the Kenyan context. Methodologically, many studies on

different contexts have embraced a descriptive research design. Kuria and Kimutai (2018) embraced a descriptive research design. This enquiry adopted a descriptive research design as it has been used by the previous researchers with consideration made to the four variables for the enquiry.

In light of the mentioned shortcomings, this present enquiry pursues at linking the disparity in knowledge that the preceding research failed to capture in addition to determine the factors affecting performance of non-governmental organizations in Nairobi County. This research consequently purposes to answer the subsequent question: How does the organizational commitment, determine the performance of NGOs in Nairobi County?

3. LITERATURE REVIEW

Organizational commitment can be described as a form of belief or culture that binds feelings of organizational values and objectives with personal values and objectives (Dachuan & Hueryren, 2017). Additionally, organizational commitment can further be described as a personal manifestation of allegiance and dedication to an organization. It is thus a comparative strength of an individual's documentation with and involvement in a given enterprise and it represents a high level of affection, loyalty and concentration on the operations of a given organization.

Organizational commitment shows that individual goals are in congruent with those of the organization and thus the individual has placed the organizational needs, goals and objectives before personal goals which leads to high productivity of the employee. It is through this commitment that leads to the organization being committed to meeting its goals and mission by having employees commit to individual assignments. High organizational commitment is beneficial to an organization because it signifies that employee have a high organizational identification (Shahida, 2019). Organizational commitment is comprised of five factors namely, strong intention to maintain membership within the organization, acceptance of the organization main objectives, a strong intent to work towards organizational objectives, a positive evaluation within the organization and a readiness to apply major work on behalf of the organization (Suharto, Suyanto, & Nedi, 2019).

In Indonesia, Suharto, Suyanto, & Nedi, (2019) undertook an enquiry to conclude the effect of organizational commitment to functioning of public entities. The target population was civil servants in central Lampung regency, metro municipal and east Lampung regency. A section of 350 workers were designated for the study. The enquiry employed causal survey for the study. First-hand information was used for the study and was assembled using questionnaires which were distributed to the respondents. Assembled information was analyzed for structural modelling analysis. It was determined that organizational commitment had a progressive inspiration on job performance. In Pakistan, Shahida, (2019) explored to establish how organizational commitment was impacting on workers functioning and the overall consequence on the functioning of the organization. The target population was employees in the textile sector of Punjab. An illustration of 179 respondents was selected for the exploration. Primary information was used for the exploration and it was assembled by aid of questionnaires. The assembled information was analyzed for correlation and regression analysis and it was established out that there was a momentous and affirmative association among employee performance and organization commitment.

Oyenyi, Adeyemi, & Olaoye, (2017) undertook a study to ascertain how organizational commitment impacts on employee's job execution. The review embraced a descriptive survey research design. The focus populace was all employees working in the hospitality industry in Nigeria. A section of 75 respondents was designated from nominated hotels and restaurants in the Osun state, Nigeria. Primary information was used for the research and was assembled using structured questionnaires. Collected data was analyzed with the aid of Pearson product movement correlation coefficient and linear regression. It was discovered affective commitment and continuance commitment had a progressive but insignificant effect on job execution while normative commitment had negative but insignificant effect on job performance.

Cheche, Muathe, & Maina, (2017) studied to conclude the intervening effect of organizational commitment on the connection between employee commitment and functioning of nominated state corporations in Kenya. The examination embraced a positivistic tactic to explore the effect among and between the variables. Descriptive and explanatory research designs to describe the variables and determine the type of connection between them. The target population was all employees working in state corporations. A section of 378 workers was nominated for the study by use of multistage sampling technique. Primary information was used for the study and assembled using questionnaires. Data was analyzed using a descriptive and inferential statistics. It was determined that employee engagement impacts organizational functioning and this association is moderately weakened by organizational commitment.

4. METHODOLOGY

The study was premised on four theories namely social exchange theory, co-operative game theory, resource-based theory and Stakeholders theory. A descriptive research design was used for the study. Primary information was used for the study which was assembled using semi structured questionnaires. The first section of the questionnaire collected bio data information of the respondents while the other sections had questions from the four variables of the study. The target population was 53 non-governmental organizations operating in Nairobi County. The unit of observation was managers from the three levels of management that is the lower level, middle level and top-level managers 3 managers were selected from each of the fifty three non-governmental organizations for the study. A sample of 112 managers was selected for the study. Collected information was scrutinized for descriptive, inferential correlation and regression analysis.

5. FINDINGS

The enquiry collected information on Organizational Commitment and performance of NGOs in Nairobi County, Kenya. Data findings are presented in the table 1.

Table 1: Organizational Commitment and Performance

Organizational Commitment statements	N	Mean	Std. Deviation
OC1: Organization is committed to achievement of its set goals and objectives	99	4.40	.493
OC2: Organization’s goals are simple, measurable and attainable	99	4.60	.493
OC3: Employees are fully involved on the operations of the organization.	99	4.39	.473
OC4: Involvement of employees has led to increased efficiency in our operations	99	4.50	.507
OC5: Organizational culture is well known and by all our employees	99	4.63	.489
OC6: Culture as an organization has ensured unity of all employees.	99	4.06	.568
Valid N (listwise)	99		

The table above shows that NGOs are committed to the achievement of their set goals and objectives as depicted by a mean of 4.40 with a standard deviation of 0.493. It should be pointed out that NGOs make goals which are simple, measurable and attainable as agreed by respondents where a mean of 4.60 with a standard deviation of 0.493 was established. A mean of 4.39 with a standard deviation of 0.473 when respondents agreed that their employees were fully involved on the operations of the organizations.

This had enabled organizations to achieve more in terms of their goals as the employees felt that they were part and parcel of the organization. Additionally, respondents agreed that involving employees in the operations of the organization had led to increased efficiency in the operations where a mean of 4.50 with a standard deviation of 0.507 was found. This means that involving employees in the operations and plans of the organization meant that they had an upper hand and capacity to contribute to the wellbeing of the organization. A mean of 4.63 with a standard deviation of 0.489 was established when respondents agreed that all employees were familiar with the organizational culture. This means that organizations had established the need to train their employees and acquaint them with their culture to assimilate them in the activities of the organization.

The study determined that the organization’s culture as an organization had ensured unity of all employees where a mean of 4.06 with a standard deviation of 0.568 was determined. This means that organizational culture is key in bringing unity and understanding in an organization. These study findings agree with those of Cheche, Muathe, & Maina, (2017) who determined that employee engagement impacts organizational functioning, and this association is moderately weakened by organizational commitment.

Table 2: Regression Model

Coefficients ^a Model	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
	B	Std. Error	Beta		
(Constant)	-4.956	.574		-8.641	.000
TrOC	.625	.069	.489	9.094	.000

$$Y = -4.956 + 0.625X_1 + e$$

-4.956 is the performance of NGOs in absence of the study variables. 0.625 is the increase in performance of the NGOs in response to a unit increase in Organizational Commitment.

6. CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATION

This study concludes that Organizational Commitment in organization is a key factor that influences performance of NGOs in Nairobi County, Kenya. In addition, the influence of Organizational Commitment was found to be statistically significant and positive. In addition, this study concludes that Organizational Commitment improves the operations of NGOs in Kenya by ensuring they have simple and attainable goals, involving all employees in setting goals and having a clear culture which has led to improvement of performance in the organization. The study recommend that Organizational Commitment in relation to enhancing the performance and composition of the top management of the NGOs should be embraced and encouraged to be adopted by all organization. This is because from the study, Organizational Commitment acted as a facilitator of performance In of NGOs.

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